

Implementation and Analysis of Deep Learning-Based Methods for Detecting Defective Ultrasound Transducers

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Abstract—Ultrasound image quality and transducer integrity directly affect diagnostic accuracy. Defective transducer elements may introduce artefacts, reduce resolution, and lead to misleading findings. This paper reports a deep learning approach for detecting defective ultrasound transducers from air-test images. The method uses a two-stage pipeline in which a U-Net segments the ultrasound scan region before mask refinement and region of interest cropping for binary classification. Multiple ImageNet-pretrained architectures were evaluated under identical conditions, including VGG16, VGG19, ResNet18, ResNet34, ResNet50, ConvNeXT, a Vision Transformer, a frozen VGG16 baseline, and custom lightweight VGG16 classifier variants. Three dataset variants and four augmentation levels were also examined. Experiments were repeated over 20 random seeds and assessed using weighted F_1 -score, parameter count, inference time, non-parametric statistical tests, and an exploratory Grad-CAM++ expert review. Across all configurations, the models achieved a mean weighted F_1 -score of 0.928 ± 0.018 . ConvNeXT attained the highest aggregate mean weighted F_1 -score (0.948 ± 0.019), followed by ResNet50 (0.943 ± 0.020). However, the differences among the leading architectures were not consistently statistically significant. Lightweight CNNs, especially ResNet18 and a custom VGG16 variant, offered a favourable balance between performance and computational cost. The Vision Transformer underperformed most CNN-based models under the available data conditions. Oversampling had a more consistent effect than reverse scan conversion or generic augmentation. These findings support CNN-based analysis of air-test images as a useful addition to ultrasound quality assurance. External validation on an independent dataset remains necessary.

Index Terms—ultrasound, transducer defect detection, convolutional neural network, vision transformer, quality assurance, deep learning

I. INTRODUCTION

Ultrasound imaging depends on the integrity of the transducer. An ultrasound transducer consists of an array of piezoelectric elements that convert electrical signals into ultrasound waves and transform the returning echoes into electrical signals for image reconstruction [1]. Since these piezoelectric elements work together as an array, defects in one or more elements can affect the reconstructed image and may reduce diagnostic image quality [2]. Element degradation, reduced sensitivity, or complete element failure can produce spatially varying signal loss, contrast changes, vertical artefacts, or

local bright and dark regions. Prior studies have shown that even a small number of defective elements can reduce signal strength, while clusters of faulty elements can substantially impair resolution and scan depth [3].

Technical quality assurance (TQA) is therefore an important component of routine ultrasound operation. In ultrasound quality assurance, common procedures include visual inspection and image uniformity assessment, often using air-test images or phantom-based protocols [4], [5]. During an air-test, the transducer is operated in air. The resulting reverberation pattern is expected to be sufficiently uniform across the active scan region when the probe is functioning correctly. Deviations from this pattern may indicate damaged elements or other transducer-related problems. Manual TQA, however, requires qualified personnel, is time-consuming, and can be subjective. These limitations motivate automated methods that may support more scalable and reproducible assessment.

Automated ultrasound quality assessment has moved from hand-designed image analysis methods towards learning-based approaches. Earlier work used image uniformity analysis and systematic dark region detection to identify possible transducer defects [6]. More recent deep learning studies have used convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for detecting uniformity artefacts or for classifying phantom-based quality parameters [7], [8]. Transformer-based models have also become prominent in medical and ultrasound image analysis, although their suitability for air-test-based transducer defect detection remains insufficiently established [9]. The UltraVision project at UAS Technikum Wien [10] previously demonstrated the feasibility of VGG16-based automated detection for defective linear probes, but reported that alternative architectures did not clearly improve performance and that Grad-CAM heatmaps [11] did not consistently align with defective regions.

This study extends that line of work by systematically benchmarking CNN-based, custom lightweight, and transformer-based architectures under a shared experimental protocol. The central research question is how deep learning-based methods can be designed and applied to detect defective ultrasound transducers while balancing classification performance, computational efficiency, and interpretability.

Fig. 1. Pipeline overview. Ultrasound images are standardised and deduplicated, scan areas segmented and refined and resulting ROIs used to evaluate classification models under varying datasets and augmentations. Performance is measured via classification metrics, efficiency, and interpretability.

Four specific aspects are addressed. The first is how standard deep learning architectures compare for binary transducer defect detection. The second is whether lightweight CNNs can reach performance comparable to larger models while reducing computational cost. The third is how preprocessing and augmentation affect performance. The fourth is how a transformer-based model performs relative to CNN-based approaches under the same training and evaluation conditions.

II. METHODS

A. Study Design

The study followed an empirical machine learning design. Raw ultrasound air-test images were first standardised and cleaned. A U-Net segmentation model then generated binary masks of the scan region. The masks were refined using computer vision post-processing and used to crop each image to its relevant region of interest (ROI). The cropped ROIs were then used for binary classification into defective and non-defective transducer images. Classification results were evaluated across model architectures, dataset variants, and augmentation settings. Model comparison included predictive performance, inference efficiency, parameter count, statistical testing, and qualitative interpretability assessment.

All experiments were implemented in Python 3.12.11 using PyTorch 2.8.0 [12] and were evaluated on a workstation with an NVIDIA RTX 4070 Ti GPU, 32 GB RAM, and Windows 11. Reproducibility was addressed by fixing random seeds for PyTorch, NumPy, and Python’s built-in random module. Deterministic PyTorch behaviour was enabled through deterministic cuDNN settings. Each classification configuration was repeated over 20 independently generated random seeds.

B. Dataset

The dataset comprised ultrasound air-test scans provided by the Medical University of Vienna and the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES). The scans were routinely collected as part of the Austrian nationwide mammography screening programme and submitted to AGES [13]. Images were available in several formats, including DICOM and standard image formats. For DICOM inputs, pixel data and relevant metadata were extracted with pydicom [14], and images were standardised to PNG before downstream processing. Based on available DICOM metadata, the original dataset covered 66 ultrasound scanner models and 199 unique devices.

TABLE I
DATASET CONFIGURATIONS USED FOR CLASSIFICATION

Dataset	Train nd/def	Val nd/def	Test nd/def
Default	155 / 368	35 / 79	34 / 80
Converted	155 / 368	35 / 79	34 / 80
Oversampled	368 / 368	35 / 79	34 / 80

Images were acquired with different transducer types, including linear, curved, curved-linear, and vector-phased probes. Each scan was labelled as defective or non-defective by two experts.

The initial dataset contained 805 scans. Two defective vector-phased samples were excluded because the number of vector-phased images was too small for meaningful analysis and could have introduced bias. After this exclusion, 803 images remained. Exact duplicates were removed using pixel-wise MD5 hashing of the decoded image content [15], leaving 765 images. Near-duplicates were then identified with perceptual hashing using Pillow [16] and ImageHash [17], with a hash size of 20 and a Hamming distance threshold of at most 1. After near-duplicate removal, the final dataset contained 751 images, consisting of 527 defective and 224 non-defective scans. Only eight of these scans were curved images, which is an important limitation for generalisation to curved probes.

Three dataset configurations were evaluated, as summarised in Table I. The default dataset contained both linear and curved ultrasound scans. The converted dataset used the same split and labels but transformed all curved scans into a linearised representation using reverse scan conversion [18]. The oversampled dataset used the same validation and test sets as the default dataset but balanced the training set by oversampling non-defective training images. Oversampling was implemented by duplicating minority-class images and applying transformations such as horizontal flipping, bottom cropping, horizontal cropping, vertical stretching, brightness and contrast adjustment, and Gaussian noise. Cropping operations were disabled for curved samples to avoid truncating the scan region. Figure 2 shows the reverse scan conversion pipeline used to generate the converted dataset.

C. ROI Segmentation and Cropping

ROI extraction was included to remove irrelevant scanner background, annotations, and potential patient information before classification. A pixel-wise segmentation strategy was selected because the ultrasound scan region is more naturally represented as a continuous mask than as a rectangular bounding box. The segmentation model was based on U-Net [19], an architecture also used in prior work on ultrasound fan delineation [20]. Ground-truth masks were manually annotated in Label Studio [21].

The U-Net model was trained from scratch on images resized to 768×768 pixels. A stratified 70:15:15 split was used for training, validation, and testing. Training used AdamW with learning rate 10^{-4} and weight decay 10^{-4} , a cosine annealing scheduler with $T_{\max} = 100$ and $\eta_{\min} = 10^{-6}$,

Fig. 2. Reverse scan conversion pipeline. The figure shows the original curved image at the top. It also shows the extracted sector geometry and corner points, followed by the resulting linearised image.

automatic mixed precision [22], and 100 epochs. Batch sizes were 4 for training and 2 for validation. The loss function was Combo Loss [23], which is a combination of equally weighted binary cross-entropy and Dice loss. Segmentation training augmentation included vertical flipping, scaling and rotation, random 90-degree rotation, additive noise, brightness adjustment, and Gaussian blurring. The best checkpoint was selected according to the validation Dice score. The final U-Net achieved an Intersection over Union of 95.6% on the segmentation test set.

Post-processing enforced more geometrically consistent masks. Contours were extracted from the predicted binary mask. The largest contour was retained, together with additional contours whose area was at least 30% of the largest contour. Contours located near the image border were removed to suppress scanner annotations and metadata. The remaining contours were merged, and a convex hull was computed to create a smooth connected mask. Curved scans received additional refinement to compensate for under-segmentation near the upper corners. The mask was extended, split along the vertical midpoint, mirrored, and recombined. For linear scans, the convex hull was used directly. The final masks were applied to the original images, and all classification models operated only on the cropped ROI images.

D. Classification Models

The classification task was binary. It distinguished defective from non-defective scans. All evaluated standard models used ImageNet-pretrained weights. The standard architectures used VGG16, VGG19 [24], ResNet18, ResNet34, ResNet50 [25], ConvNeXT [26], and ViT-B/16 [27]. These models were selected to cover classical CNN baselines, residual CNNs with different depths, a modern convolutional architecture, and a transformer-based reference.

The VGG16 baseline reproduced the UltraVision-style model [10] used as a reference baseline in this study. It used a frozen ImageNet-pretrained VGG16 feature extractor with a modified classifier head of size $4096 \rightarrow 256 \rightarrow 1$. This model is denoted as VGG16 (Base). In contrast, the standard VGG16 and VGG19 models were fine-tuned end-to-end.

Custom VGG16 variants were also evaluated to test whether a smaller classifier head could improve the performance-efficiency trade-off. For these models, the original adaptive average pooling layer with output size 7×7 was replaced by global average pooling with output size 1×1 , reducing the classifier input dimensionality from $512 \times 7 \times 7$ to $512 \times 1 \times 1$. Batch normalization was introduced to stabilise optimisation [28]. Multiple classifier heads were tested by varying hidden-layer widths and dropout rates. The best-performing custom model was the medium_d01 configuration with hidden layers of 256 and 128 units and dropout rates of 0.2 and 0.1, respectively. This model is reported as VGG16 (Custom).

E. Training Protocol

Experiment management used Hydra grid sweeps [29]. Each classification configuration was trained for 15 epochs with batch size 32. Input images were converted from BGR to RGB, resized to 224×224 pixels, and normalised with ImageNet mean and standard deviation. All models were fine-tuned end-to-end except VGG16 (Base), whose backbone remained frozen. Training used BCEWithLogitsLoss with class weighting based on the training split. Optimisation used AdamW [30] with learning rate 10^{-4} and weight decay 10^{-4} , together with cosine annealing using $T_{\max} = 15$ and $\eta_{\min} = 10^{-6}$. The checkpoint with the highest validation F_1 -score was retained.

The classification threshold was optimised on the validation set. Validation logits were converted to probabilities using the sigmoid function, and thresholds from 0.05 to 0.95 in steps of 0.01 were evaluated. The threshold maximising the validation F_1 -score was selected, with ties resolved by the first threshold that reached the maximum.

Four augmentation strategies were compared during classification training, which were none, light, medium, and strong. Light augmentation applied horizontal flipping with probability 0.2, crop-and-stretch with probability 0.1 and magnitude 5–10%, and brightness or contrast changes with probability 0.1 and magnitude 5%. Medium augmentation increased these probabilities to 0.3, 0.2, and 0.2, respectively, used crop-and-stretch magnitudes of 5–15%, and added Gaussian blur with probability 0.1. Strong augmentation used horizontal flipping with probability 0.5, crop-and-stretch with probability 0.3

and magnitude 10–20%, brightness or contrast changes with probability 0.3 and magnitude 10%, and Gaussian blur with probability 0.2.

F. Evaluation and Statistical Analysis

The primary metric was weighted F_1 -score, selected because the dataset was class-imbalanced. Mean test accuracy was also computed as a secondary descriptive metric for aggregate comparison with prior work. Defective scans were treated as the positive class.

Computational efficiency was evaluated through model parameter count and mean inference time per sample in milliseconds. Inference time was measured on the RTX 4070 Ti in evaluation mode using `torch.no_grad()` and CUDA events during test-set evaluation.

Model comparisons across 20 seeds used non-parametric tests. Overall differences were assessed with the Friedman test, with Kendall’s W reported as the effect size. Post-hoc pairwise comparisons employed Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Benjamini–Hochberg correction ($\alpha = 0.05$).

G. Interpretability Assessment

To complement quantitative model comparison, Grad-CAM++ heatmaps [31] were generated for the two most efficient candidate models, ResNet18 and VGG16 (Custom). The selected layers were `layer3[-1]` for ResNet18 and `features[26]` for VGG16, corresponding to the second convolution in the fifth VGG feature block. These layers were chosen because preliminary analysis indicated comparatively good visual alignment with defective regions.

Twenty-five images were randomly sampled using a fixed seed of 42. Heatmap presentation order was randomized using the same seed. A single ultrasound expert performed a blinded side-by-side assessment. For each image, the expert assigned an alignment score from 1 to 4, where 1 indicated no alignment and 4 indicated good alignment, and selected the preferred heatmap when applicable. Because the assessment involved one expert and 25 images, it was treated as exploratory rather than statistically generalizable evidence.

III. RESULTS

A. Overall Model Performance

Across all models, datasets, and augmentation settings, the experiments achieved stable classification performance with a mean weighted F_1 -score of 0.928 ± 0.018 . Table II summarises aggregate weighted F_1 -score, mean test accuracy, inference time, and parameter count for the main evaluated models. ConvNeXT achieved the highest mean weighted F_1 -score (0.9481 ± 0.0188), followed by ResNet50 (0.9435 ± 0.0198) and ResNet34 (0.9381 ± 0.0235). VGG16 (Custom) and ResNet18 remained competitive, with mean weighted F_1 -scores of 0.9324 ± 0.0227 and 0.9302 ± 0.0231 , respectively. Standard VGG16 and VGG19 produced slightly lower aggregate scores. VGG16 (Base), with its frozen feature extractor, had the weakest aggregate performance (0.8876 ± 0.0287).

TABLE II
AGGREGATE MODEL PERFORMANCE ACROSS DATASETS AND AUGMENTATIONS

Model	F_1	Acc.	ms	Params (M)
ResNet18	0.9302	0.9362	3.355	11.18
VGG16 (Custom)	0.9324	0.9380	3.125	14.88
ResNet34	0.9381	0.9414	4.981	21.29
ResNet50	0.9435	0.9490	5.843	23.51
VGG16 (Base)	0.8876	0.9005	3.136	21.14
ConvNeXT	0.9481	0.9534	8.497	87.57
ViT	0.9194	0.9252	5.595	85.80
VGG16	0.9276	0.9310	4.225	134.26
VGG19	0.9292	0.9330	5.621	139.57

The custom VGG16 classifier variants were first compared on the oversampled dataset under strong augmentation. Their mean weighted F_1 -scores ranged from 0.9257 to 0.9427. The medium_d01 classifier achieved the highest mean score, but the Friedman test did not indicate a statistically significant difference among custom variants ($p = 0.4066$). The medium_d01 variant was therefore selected as the representative VGG16 (Custom) model for the remaining comparisons because it had the best numerical performance.

Under the fixed setting of the default dataset with strong augmentation, the Vision Transformer (ViT) reached a mean weighted F_1 -score of 0.9135. It performed significantly worse than ConvNeXT and ResNet34, while being statistically indistinguishable from VGG19 in that setting. In the aggregate comparison, ViT achieved 0.9194 ± 0.0263 , which was lower than all CNN-based models except VGG16 (Base). Despite having a parameter count similar to ConvNeXT, ViT underperformed ConvNeXT by approximately 0.029 weighted F_1 -score in aggregate and by approximately 0.027 in the default strong-augmentation setting. These results indicate that, under the available data conditions and training protocol, the evaluated CNN models were generally more suitable than the transformer baseline.

B. Effect of Dataset Preprocessing

Figure 3 compares weighted F_1 -scores across the default, converted, and oversampled dataset variants under strong augmentation. Oversampling produced the strongest results overall. On the oversampled dataset, ConvNeXT achieved the highest mean weighted F_1 -score (0.9572), followed closely by ResNet50 (0.9550). On the default dataset, ConvNeXT (0.9405) and ResNet34 (0.9396) were the strongest models. On the converted dataset, ResNet50 reached the highest mean weighted F_1 -score (0.9437), followed by ConvNeXT (0.9398).

Table III reports mean weighted F_1 -scores for each model and dataset variant under strong augmentation. Per-model Friedman tests showed that preprocessing had a statistically significant effect for ConvNeXT ($p = 0.016$), ResNet50 ($p < 0.001$), VGG16 (Base) ($p < 0.001$), ViT ($p < 0.001$), and VGG16 (Custom) ($p = 0.008$). No statistically significant preprocessing effect was observed for ResNet18, ResNet34, VGG16, or VGG19.

Fig. 3. Weighted F_1 -scores across all evaluated models across the default_nd155_def368, converted_nd155_def368, and oversampled_nd368_def368 dataset variants under strong augmentation. Statistical significance is encoded as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$ after Benjamini-Hochberg correction.

TABLE III
MEAN WEIGHTED F_1 -SCORE BY DATASET VARIANT UNDER STRONG AUGMENTATION

Model	Default	Converted	Oversampled
ConvNeXT	0.9405	0.9398	0.9572
ResNet18	0.9248	0.9201	0.9301
ResNet34	0.9396	0.9295	0.9428
ResNet50	0.9250	0.9437	0.9550
VGG16 (Custom)	0.9321	0.9190	0.9427
VGG16	0.9284	0.9207	0.9251
VGG16 (Base)	0.8658	0.8679	0.9041
VGG19	0.9239	0.9249	0.9321
ViT	0.9135	0.9109	0.9387

The significant effects were primarily driven by the oversampled dataset. ConvNeXT performed significantly better on the oversampled dataset than on both the default and converted datasets. ResNet50 showed the clearest ordering. The oversampled dataset performed better than the converted dataset, which in turn outperformed the default dataset. VGG16 (Base) and ViT also benefited substantially from oversampling. VGG16 (Custom) showed a significant improvement for oversampled relative to converted. These findings suggest that balancing the class distribution by oversampling was more beneficial than reverse scan conversion for most evaluated architectures.

Reverse scan conversion did not provide a universal advantage. Except for ResNet50, whose mean weighted F_1 -score increased from 0.9250 to 0.9437, none of the other models consistently improved relative to the default dataset.

Fig. 4. Weighted F_1 -scores of all evaluated models across augmentation strategies on the oversampled_nd368_def368 dataset. Statistical significance is encoded as * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, and *** $p < 0.001$ after Benjamini-Hochberg correction.

This indicates that geometric normalisation through reverse scan conversion may be task-dependent and may not transfer directly from anatomical ultrasound classification to air-test-based defect detection.

C. Effect of Data Augmentation

Because the oversampled dataset produced the strongest overall performance, the effect of augmentation was examined on that dataset. Figure 4 shows the corresponding comparison across no, light, medium, and strong augmentation.

Augmentation effects were weaker and less consistent than dataset preprocessing effects. ConvNeXT achieved the highest mean weighted F_1 -score with no augmentation (0.9576) and nearly identical performance with strong augmentation (0.9572). ResNet50 reached its highest value under strong augmentation (0.9550), while ResNet18 achieved its highest value under medium augmentation (0.9416). The Vision Transformer showed the largest augmentation-related improvement, increasing from 0.8995 without augmentation to 0.9387 under strong augmentation. VGG16 improved from 0.9219 without augmentation to 0.9400 under light augmentation.

Friedman tests found statistically significant augmentation effects for ConvNeXT ($p = 0.029$), VGG16 ($p = 0.006$), ViT ($p < 0.001$), and VGG16 (Base) ($p = 0.034$). For VGG16 (Base), however, no pairwise post-hoc comparison remained significant after Benjamini-Hochberg correction. No statistically significant augmentation effects were observed for ResNet18, ResNet34, ResNet50, VGG19, or VGG16 (Custom). For ConvNeXT, no augmentation and strong augmen-

TABLE IV
MEAN WEIGHTED F_1 -SCORE ON THE OVERSAMPLED DATASET BY
AUGMENTATION STRATEGY

Model	None	Light	Medium	Strong
ConvNeXT	0.9576	0.9512	0.9425	0.9572
ResNet18	0.9335	0.9310	0.9416	0.9301
ResNet34	0.9431	0.9351	0.9383	0.9428
ResNet50	0.9477	0.9445	0.9450	0.9550
VGG16 (Custom)	0.9255	0.9367	0.9385	0.9427
VGG16	0.9219	0.9400	0.9296	0.9251
VGG16 (Base)	0.8865	0.9063	0.8949	0.9041
VGG19	0.9305	0.9328	0.9309	0.9321
ViT	0.8995	0.9262	0.9299	0.9387

Fig. 5. Comparison of mean weighted F_1 -score to parameter count for all evaluated models, aggregated across all datasets and augmentation strategies. Error bars indicate the standard deviation.

tation significantly outperformed medium augmentation. For VGG16, light augmentation significantly outperformed no augmentation. For ViT, light, medium, and strong augmentation all significantly outperformed no augmentation. These results indicate that augmentation is architecture-dependent and should not be assumed to improve performance uniformly.

D. Performance-Efficiency Trade-Off

Figure 5 summarises the performance-efficiency analysis. The aggregate results show that larger models did not necessarily produce better results. ConvNeXT achieved the highest mean weighted F_1 -score, but required 87.6 million parameters and had the slowest mean inference time at 8.497 ms per sample. ResNet50 provided strong performance with 23.5 million parameters and 5.843 ms per sample. ResNet18 and VGG16 (Custom) had lower aggregate F_1 -scores than ConvNeXT and ResNet50, but their computational requirements were substantially smaller.

ResNet18 achieved 0.9302 ± 0.0231 weighted F_1 -score with 11.18 million parameters and 3.355 ms inference time. VGG16 (Custom) achieved 0.9324 ± 0.0227 weighted F_1 -score with 14.88 million parameters and 3.125 ms inference time, the lowest reported inference time among evaluated models. The performance gap between these lightweight models and ResNet50 was 0.0133 for ResNet18 and 0.0111 for VGG16 (Custom). Relative to ConvNeXT, the gaps were 0.0179 and 0.0157, respectively. These differences are small relative to the reductions in parameter count and runtime. ResNet18

and VGG16 (Custom) are therefore suitable options when computational efficiency is a primary consideration.

The large VGG models were not efficient choices in this setting. Standard VGG16 and VGG19 required 134.26 million and 139.57 million parameters, respectively, yet achieved lower aggregate weighted F_1 -scores than ResNet18, VGG16 (Custom), ResNet34, ResNet50, and ConvNeXT. ViT also required 85.80 million parameters and did not outperform the lightweight CNNs. Thus, model size alone was not a reliable predictor of classification performance for this task.

E. Interpretability Results

The exploratory Grad-CAM++ assessment did not show a clear qualitative advantage for either ResNet18 or VGG16 (Custom). ResNet18 received a total expert alignment score of 52, while VGG16 (Custom) received 50. The expert preferred ResNet18 heatmaps in 12 cases and VGG16 (Custom) heatmaps in 10 cases, with no preference in the remaining cases. A paired Wilcoxon signed-rank test found no statistically significant difference between the two models ($p = 0.921$).

Some heatmaps highlighted salient image regions that did not correspond to expert-identified defective transducer areas. The interpretability analysis therefore supports qualitative inspection of model behaviour, but it should not be interpreted as precise defect localisation. It is best regarded as supplementary evidence rather than as a stand-alone basis for clinical or technical maintenance decisions.

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Principal Findings

The results indicate that deep learning models can detect defective ultrasound transducers from air-test images with high weighted F_1 -scores within the available dataset. ConvNeXT had the strongest aggregate numerical performance, followed by ResNet50 and ResNet34. However, the differences among leading models were not consistently significant across experimental settings. This weakens any claim of a single universally superior architecture and shifts practical model selection towards secondary criteria such as computational efficiency, robustness across preprocessing conditions, and interpretability. The frozen VGG16 baseline underperformed the fine-tuned alternatives, supporting end-to-end adaptation to the ultrasound air-test domain. The custom VGG16 model substantially reduced parameter count and inference time while maintaining competitive performance.

The comparison between CNNs and the Vision Transformer suggests that the evaluated transformer baseline was less suitable under the present data conditions. ViT improved markedly with augmentation, but its aggregate performance remained below that of most CNNs despite a high parameter count. This finding does not exclude transformer-based approaches in general. Instead, it indicates that the tested ViT-B/16 configuration and training regime were not the best match for the available dataset size and task structure.

B. Preprocessing and Augmentation

Preprocessing had a broader effect than augmentation. Oversampling was the most effective dataset-level intervention, particularly for models that appeared more affected by the original class imbalance. Reverse scan conversion was less consistently beneficial. Although it improved ResNet50 relative to the default dataset, it did not improve most other architectures. This suggests that the value of converting curved scan geometry to a linearised representation depends on the model and task. Interpretation remains limited by the very small number of curved scans in the final dataset.

Augmentation effects were model-specific. ConvNeXT performed best with no augmentation or strong augmentation and worse with medium augmentation. VGG16 benefited from light augmentation. ViT benefited from any augmentation relative to no augmentation, with the strongest score under strong augmentation. Several models showed no statistically significant augmentation effect. These findings emphasize that augmentation should be validated empirically for each architecture and dataset rather than selected as a generic default.

C. Practical Implications

The results support automated air-test screening as a decision-support tool for ultrasound quality assurance. Such a system could reduce manual workload, standardise initial screening, and flag images that require expert review. Since false negatives could allow defective transducers to remain in use and false positives could trigger unnecessary maintenance, the system should not be fully autonomous without further validation. Its most appropriate role is as a screening or triage component integrated into a quality assurance workflow.

For deployment-oriented scenarios, ResNet18 and VGG16 (Custom) are suitable candidates because they combine competitive F_1 -scores with low parameter count and short inference time. If computational resources are less constrained and maximum aggregate classification performance is the main objective, ConvNeXT or ResNet50 may be preferable. ResNet50 is a suitable intermediate option because it approaches ConvNeXT performance with far fewer parameters and lower inference time.

D. Comparison with Prior Work

The findings are consistent with earlier work indicating that automated ultrasound quality assessment is feasible. Compared with the reproduced UltraVision baseline, VGG16 (Custom) improved aggregate mean test accuracy under the present experimental setup from about 90% to 94%. The ResNet18 results also align with prior CNN-based uniformity artefact detection work, supporting residual CNNs as reliable candidates for ultrasound quality assessment.

The results differ from prior work, where reverse scan conversion showed broader benefits. Here, it improved only ResNet50, which may reflect task differences between anatomical ultrasound classification and air-test-based defect detection. Unlike anatomical imaging, air-test data primarily capture

probe behaviour and reverberation artefacts, so geometric normalisation may have a different effect.

E. Limitations

The main limitation is the dataset size and composition. After cleaning and deduplication, 751 images remained, with 527 defective and 224 non-defective scans. Only eight images were curved scans. Consequently, the models are expected to generalise better to linear probes than to curved probes.

The interpretability analysis was exploratory. It used 25 images and one expert, and Grad-CAM++ is an approximate post-hoc method. Heatmap alignment should not be interpreted as exact defect localisation. More rigorous localisation would require region-level annotations, such as bounding boxes or segmentation masks for defective regions, and evaluation by multiple experts.

F. Future Work

Future work should prioritise larger and more balanced datasets, particularly for curved probes. A larger curved-probe subset would allow a more reliable assessment of reverse scan conversion and geometry-specific model behaviour. External validation on data from independent institutions and acquisition conditions is necessary to establish robustness.

Future studies should also move beyond image-level classification towards explicit defect localisation. This would require detailed labels for defective regions but could produce outputs that are more directly useful to quality assurance personnel. Additional model families, including lightweight multi-scale CNNs, feature-pyramid architectures, attention-enhanced CNNs, and hybrid CNN-transformer approaches, should also be evaluated under comparable conditions.

V. CONCLUSION

These results indicate that CNN-based models can detect defective ultrasound transducers from air-test images with high weighted F_1 -scores in the available dataset. ConvNeXT achieved the highest aggregate score, but differences among the leading models were not consistently significant. Lightweight CNNs, especially ResNet18 and VGG16 (Custom), provided a favourable balance between classification performance, parameter count, and inference time. Oversampling improved performance more consistently than reverse scan conversion or generic augmentation, while the Vision Transformer underperformed most CNN-based alternatives. Automated air-test image analysis therefore appears to be a useful supplement to ultrasound quality assurance, but independent external validation and larger balanced datasets are required before these findings can be generalised.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Lorenz Flich conducted the research as part of the master's thesis, including study conception, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. The full master's thesis is available from the library of the UAS Technikum Wien. FH-Prof. Priv.-Doz. Dipl.-Ing.(FH) Dr. Bernhard Knapp supervised the

research process on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance, critically reviewed the manuscript. Christian Kollmann provided expert guidance on ultrasound imaging and advised on the ultrasound-specific aspects of the study.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The ultrasound air-test scans used in this study were provided by the Medical University of Vienna and the Austrian Agency for Health and Food Safety (AGES) as part of the Austrian nationwide mammography screening programme and are not publicly available. The source code used for data pre-processing, model training, and evaluation is publicly available at <https://github.com/LorenzFlich/transducer-defect-detection>.

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